

The Logic within the Logic **Reinterpretation of Boolean algebra from Transcursive Logic**

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ABSTRACT

In the introduction of Boole's "Mathematical Analysis of Logic" of 1847, he approaches one of the operative foundations of Transcursive Logic. He tells us that "those who are familiar with the theory of symbolic algebra, know that the validity of their analysis does not depend on the interpretation of the symbols, but only on the laws of their combination." This statement makes very clear the preponderance that Boole gives to relationships. In response to this interest in the relational, we proposed to try to understand, how it was that Boole gave an algebraic form to logic. To carry out this task, we decided to use the principles that govern Transcursive Logic (TL). The analysis of the categorical propositions was initiated: universal affirmative, universal negative, particular affirmative and particular negative. In analyzing the latter, we discovered that a whole universe could be described only from it. That is, not only told us that, for example, "some **a** is not **b**", but also could tell us: that there is "**a** which are not **b**", that there is "**b** that is not **a**", that there is "**a** which is **b**", and that in the rest of the universe there is "something" that "is not **a** nor is **b**". Then, from the TL it was inquired about the relationships that link these contents to try to determine how this algebraic structure could be generated. After some steps, four elements that resulted from this inquiry were given an entity; by relating them, they formed an algebraic structure called the permutation group or Galois group. The structure that constitutes the "universal language" in which the TL is written. In the analysis of the basic principles on which Boole's algebra is based, we have discovered that some aspects of reality that are revealed when we approach it from the subjective hidden between its values of truth and functions. That is, there is an 'implicit logic' underlying the Boolean binary proposal, a logic that we have called 'transcursive' because it leaves evidence of a particular evolution over time, of what affects an observer. Among the findings, are: a) the existence of a complex system based, not on its constituent elements and a specific purpose, but on the interrelations that link its components. b) a systemic complexity that enables an adaptive dynamic response in front of the demands (inputs). c) the possibility of analyzing through the discovered structure, the relational situation of several binary systems, simultaneously (heterarchical distribution of hierarchical systems). d) the functional non-dependence of the structure concerning the observer (measurement process), as it is the case with any situation that is objectively addressed, and e) the advantage of being able to consider situations where more than two states are at stake, even if they are exclusive. From the transcursive perspective, an interesting panorama opens up of possible applications of this way of observing reality.

Keyword: logic, Boolean algebra, subjective reality, transcursive logic.

CITATION:

Salatino, D. R. (2019). "The logic within the logic. Reinterpretation of Boolean algebra from Transcursive Logic" *Inter. J. Res. Methodol. Soc. Sci.*, Vol., 5, No. 1: pp. 83-99. (Jan. – Mar. 2019); ISSN: 2415-0371. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.2667559

1.0 INTRODUCTION

“They who are acquainted with the present state of the theory of Symbolical Algebra, are aware, that the validity of the processes of analysis does not depend upon the interpretation of the symbols which are employed, but solely upon the laws of their combination.” George Boole, 1847, p. 3.

The introduction that Boole makes in his “Mathematical Analysis of Logic” approaches one of the operative foundations of Transcursive Logic (TL), which is to generate a structure that can be modified using functions. Even more so when he completes it by saying: "Any system of interpretation that does not affect the truth of the supposed relationships is equally admissible."

To understand how Boole gave an algebraic form to logic, we will use the TL principles; we will approach it from the perspective of the subject. We undertake this task knowing that logic, from its beginnings, was defined as objective. Thus, in the first book of the Aristotelian “First Analytical,” there is no mention of subjective factors. It is not since Aristotle where modern logic takes its severe objective attitude, but from the mathematics that he wanted to imitate in the initial Boolean period. (Bochenski, 1981, p.10)

A Boolean algebra is an 'algebraic structure', that is, a classifier of sets according to the elements they contain and is defined by any set in which we have, at least, two different and opposite elements to represent them, let's say '1' for affirmation and '0' for its opposite, denial (Del Vado Virseda, 2017, p.80). We appeal to the Euler logical diagrams to better understand this structure.

Fig. 1. Categorical proposition

(Image of the original, Euler, 1768, p.101)

"Since a general notion contains an infinity of individual objects, it is considered space where all individuals are contained. Thus, for the notion of 'man,' we create a space where all men are contained. For the notion of 'mortal,' we also create a space where all mortals will be contained. Then, when I say that all men are mortal, it is equivalent to the fact that the first figure is contained in the second." (Euler, 1768, Lettre CII, p.98)
 (Own Translation).

Thus, Euler represented four categorical propositions: universal affirmative, universal negative, particular affirmative and particular negative (Figure 1).

2.0 PARTICULAR NEGATIVE PROPOSITION - A NEW UNIVERSE

We will take the particular *negative proposition: some A is not B*, to face our analysis of Boole's work (Figure 2).

Fig. 2. Particular negative production

Figure 2 shows that in the superposition of two sets, in fact, four general regions are formed. Let's see: of a universal or fundamental set U, we can say that it is 'inhabited' by two subsets: **A** and **B**, which when 'overlapping,' shows us that there is a subset of **a** that is not **b** (01). That there is also a subset of **b** that is not **a** (10). And instead of *some, a is not b*; there is a subset of **a** that is also **b** (11). All these subsets are 'inhabiting' a universe U where there is no more **a** nor **b** (00) than those cited (Nahin, 2013, p.45).

Suppose that **A** represents women and **B** represents the right-handed people of this universe. The scheme is showing us that the universe U is populated by left-handed women (01), by right-handed men (10), by right-handed women (11), and by left-handed men (00). Then, the previous graphic rather than telling us that *some woman is not right-handed* shows us all the content of that universe and its distribution. That is, it identifies the diverse content of the structure.

3.0 ALGEBRAIC STRUCTURE

The TL also inquired about the relationships that link the previous contents. Next, we will see how this algebraic structure could have been generated.

Let U be an *ad hoc* universe that determines the *scope* (See Appendix A) of a given *function* and *A class* (See Appendix A) included in this universe, which we will generically call "disorder", and which represents the *domain* (See Appendix A) of such a function (Figure 3).

Fig. 3. Universe

We will call in turn, *ambit* or *contecture* of **A** to the set of elements that belong to it. In this case, the "disorder" and we will denominate content of **A**, all the elements that do not belong to it.

That is to say, what belongs to its *complement* (**B**) that will also be a contexture and that generically we will call “order” (absence of disorder).

If we symbolize with "1", the belonging to the *ambit*, the belonging to the *content*, we will do it with "0" (Figure 4).

Fig. 4. Contexture-universe relationship

For any element of **U**, each contexture is determined, in reality, by two values (Figure 5) that are interpreted in the following way: '1' belongs to the contexture considered and '0' belongs to the "complementary contexture" (its absence).

Fig. 5. Contexture

This pair of values is linked to a double relationship: they are opposite (one is the negation of the other), and they are complementary (added together give the unit). The same is true considering them in pairs. If we represent **A** and **B** by their "contexture values" and in a paired form, we have **0110**. If we deny (we determine the opposite of) these values, we obtain **1001**. This could be defined as the establishment of a cyclical dynamic that would be given by the tendency to go towards “order” (10) through “disorder” (01) and vice versa. Also, as the group of transformations necessary to preserve the symmetry of an algebraic invariant (Noether, 1908, 1918), as we shall see. This dynamic becomes evident when we successively deny a contexture in its entirety, without being annulled, as in the traditional negation (See Appendix A). Everything happens as if he denied the "continent" of the elements belonging to the contexture and not the property of the elements themselves (the content). This dynamic is a dyadic relationship (links two classes) established between classes of “ordered pairs” of values (See Appendix A).

3.1 Function

There is another type of relationship that can be established in this universe. This relationship is of a particular type that we will call 'functional relationship' or *function*. Here, function assigns an element of the **contexture** or *continent* to an element of the *content*. We say that the *function* projects the *continent* in the *content*. Or in another way, a set of structures is projected in another set of structures. We will call this projection *transformation* or change. (Figure 6).

Fig. 6. Function or transformation

For each structure that “enters” into the transformation there is a structure that “leaves” it. With this, we characterize a “third contexture” in our universe (Figure 7). This contexture is not evident when we consider the static universe, but when we put it in "movement" through successive denials of the continent of our "base contexture," a "mediating contexture" appears that leaves a record of this happening in its structure. The way it has to record what happened is "trapping" in its own continent the elements that define the content of each "related contexture." For that reason, its representation is 11, which certifies that both "opposite poles" (continent and content) of our original universe, are simultaneous. We will call this new contexture "organization".

Fig. 7. Organization

The organization transcends the mere structure to leave evidence of the interrelation between two contextures. It manages the "place" for two values (those of the contextures it relates), acting, as well as a kind of "memory" of bivalent system distribution, which, being denied in this way, does not disappear.

It is created like this a triadic relationship (because it relates three contextures) that registers a "mediated negation" (Hegel, 2011, p.419). The passage from one pole to its opposite (something that promotes any negation) is "mediated" by a transformation. Therefore, the pole of origin (argument or **domain** of the function, Source of change) does not disappear but is represented in the structure (scope or continent) of the "mediating contexture" so that, in a later step, it can reach the opposite pole (value or **co-domain** of the function. Destination of the change), having conserved the origin pole (both poles are present simultaneously, despite being exclusive). If we change the binary numbers (01,11,10) by their decimal equivalents (1,3,2) we see that the negation of 1 (01) is not 2 (10) (its opposite pole) but 3 (11) and that the negation of 3 (11) is not 0 (00) (the opposite of 11 is 00) but 2 (10). Mediated negation is really a conservative displacement, such as Hegel's *aufheben*, or the "as if" of Hans Vaihinger (1911).

It should be noted that the structure that we have outlined does not follow the laws of classical logic as does the structure defined by Boole. For example, the negation of the negation (double negation) does not give an affirmation (the same element from which it came out – See Appendix A), but as a result, the opposite pole is obtained (as in a traditional negation), without losing the terms involved. This mechanism also does not follow two of the basic principles of the

Aristotelian logic, which Boole does respect (See Appendix A). The 'principle of non-contradiction', since the opposite ends are both present in the same situation and the 'principle of the excluded third', already that between one end and the other there is a third entity that has common elements with the two extremes (in equal parts), and is also present simultaneously with them.

This triadic relation created, in our opinion, adequately represents a 'living' universe (it can evolve) in one of its basic aspects: its superficial or apparent structure. We call this structure complex because its elements have a triple relationship with each other, they are opposites, complementary and concurrent (or simultaneous) (Morin, 1977, p.101).

3.2 Structure

Why do we say that what we have just analyzed is a structure? We say it because it complies with the guidelines established by Piaget (1985, p.6) for all structures. Let's see:

1°) It is a set of transformations that involves laws as a whole (as opposed to the properties of the elements) that is conserved or enriched by the same game of its transformations without these reaching a result outside its borders or claiming some exterior elements. That is, it complies with the following characteristics:

- totality
- transformation
- self-regulation

Let us analyze it carefully under the three characters posed by Piaget:

- It is a whole because it is made up of elements subordinated to the laws that characterize the set (laws or compositional operations) that are not reduced to 'cumulative associations' but give this set, properties different from those of the constituent elements. As Piaget says, what counts is not the elements, nor the whole, but the relations between the elements. The whole is the result of the relations of composition whose laws are what determine the whole through its unity.

- There is a transformation that in our case is a function, the change that plays an organizational role.

- There is self-adjustment (self-regulation) because there is conservation and 'certain closure' since the process does not lead beyond its borders, generating elements that only belong to the structure and thus preserve its laws. That is, it respects the laws of symmetry: conservation and invariance (Noether, 1918).

3.3 Composition operation

What is the law or operation of composition in this case? The whole structure that we have tried to determine starts with two values: 0 and 1 (as in the algebraic structure of Boole) that represent the 'absence' and the 'presence' of a single element, respectively.

As we saw, the function is a method to assign to each element of its scope, a single element of its domain. Theoretically, the number (N) of these functions can be infinite and depends on 1) the number (n) of class variables (in this case it is equal to 1, and we will call it S); 2) the number (m) of class values, in this case is equal to 2: '0' and '1', and 3) the number (c) of combinations that we can make of these two values. The formula (Peirce, 1958, CP.4,260) that allows us to calculate the number of possible functions is: $N = C^{m^n}$ therefore, $N = 2^{2^1} = 4 \text{ functions}$. These functions (f_n) can be expressed as shown in Table I.

Table 1. Functions

	f_1	f_2	f_3	f_4	
S	3	2	1	0	→ decimal
0	1	1	0	0	
1	1	0	1	0	
	V	O	S	∇	→ contextures
	\bar{S}^*			\bar{V}^{**}	

*It means No S or denial of S and is equivalent to O

** It means No V or denial of V and is equivalent to ∇

Table I shows that each of the detailed functions constitutes a contexture to which we have assigned a name, in addition to its decimal equivalent. Other details to consider are a) the contextures of the second half of the table (S and ∇) are complementary and opposed to those of the first half (V and O), and b) the contexture S is the contexture of which we start (S = 01 = 1).

In class logic, class operations serve to compose complex classes from simple classes. These operations are: union, intersection, and complement.

The union of classes (U) has the same properties as the inclusive (inclusive) disjunction between propositions (although here it is not a truth function). An intersection of classes (∩) has the properties of a propositional conjunction. The complement of a class (~) has the properties of a propositional negation.

The only possible operation between S and O so that both values obtained are true (1) is the union (governed by the propositional disjunction), which is expressed in contexture V. Now, if we remember what V represents, we observe that this operation it is a very particular union (disjunction).

A contexture is different from another when there is at least one property that is not common to it, and that property may not belong to the contexture in question. It is enough that it can be attributed to one or the other, but not both simultaneously. Therefore, what V expresses is that only the different properties of the contextures it relates are included in its scope, excluding the equal properties. This union is called exclusive (as opposed to inclusive that contemplates or includes the same properties) and has the same properties as the exclusive disjunction (XOR).

Then the definition here would be: "An element belongs to the scope of the exclusive union of two contextures (A⊕B) when it belongs at least to the scope of one of them. And it will not belong to the scope of this union when it belongs to the scope or content of both." (Fig. 8).

Fig. 8. XOR

If we apply this operation to our textures, we will see what is shown in the lower part of Figure 8. The union of the successive contextures results in the following contexture. There is a 'displacement' equal to that recorded during the successive negations N1 and N2. This confirms that the composition operation of our triadic structure is \oplus (exclusive disjunction or XOR). If we apply this operation once again to our structure, we will verify that it is equivalent to a third negation: N3.

The result surprises us: the obtained contexture is the one from where we left: S (01). This constitutes a structure of cyclical appearance as shown in Figure 9.

Fig. 9. Superficial cyclical structure

Now this surface structure of U is complete. A structure that cycles "jumps" (See Appendix A) through time, indefinitely, posing a kind of "relationship" between the "real" actors of this universe.

3.4 Profound cyclical structure

In the reality of this proposed universe never better characterized this process that we have seen as superficial or apparent structure since, it is not the only thing that happens.

If we look closely at Figure 9, we will notice that the third negation (N₃): the displacement of O (10) → S (01), is not different from a classic negation. Then, why did not O (10) disappear?

The explanation is that N₃ appears to be a classic negation, but in reality, it is a 'mediated negation' of a change; that is, it is the product of a function.

This change to which we allude is 'hidden,' is not apparent and also has characteristics of being "cumulative." The reason that it is "not seen" is that just as the contexture representing the evident change captured within its ambit, the ambit of the contextures that is related (11). Here is a contexture that captures the contents of both related classes (00). If V (11) represented the co-presence of the poles, ∇ (00) represents the co-absence of them (Figure 10).

Fig. 10. Transformation or hidden change

The null value (00 - decimal: 0) makes this new contexture: ∇ , 'invisible' (See Appendix A). This is so because it captures in its own content, the content of the related contextures, leaving evidence of the process of displacement and avoiding the disappearance of O (10), as it would have happened in a classical negation.

As there must be coherence in the system, necessarily, a series of operations must be carried out to justify this mediated displacement and demonstrate why S (01) is reached in spite of such operations.

The intervention of a new contexture: ∇ (00), 'hidden,' produces a point of inflection in the surface structure, evident or discrete.

As shown in Figure 10, the intermediate step ∇ (00) between O (10) and V (11) (hidden) generates a pole opposite V (11); that is, its complement (and its opposite or negation). This complement is in every way, even in the fact of being the opposite of the apparent. Now V (11) is complete as a contexture since it acquires its content.

We can suppose, that the operation of composition that binds this new contexture ∇ to the already existing poles S and O, must be opposite to XOR.

This operation exists and is called *equivalence* or XNOR. This equivalence is based on the formal properties of propositional biconditionality (double implication) (we insist, here it is not a truth function). Its definition in our case would be: "An element belongs to the content of the intersection of two classes ($A \cap B$), when it belongs to the content of both classes; and it will not belong to the content of the intersection, when it belongs only to the content of one of them ". In graphics and symbols, it is shown in Figure 11.

Fig. 11. Equivalence

If we apply the operation described the new contexture, we will have what is shown in the lower part of Figure 11. As in the superficial structure, the successive application of the suggested operation is equivalent to the successive negations, since it "cycles" through the different contextures. Applying once again the *equivalence* we arrive at the beginning of the cycle that in this case is of recursive or recurrent type and which we call "reflective."

A new triadic structure is thus proposed that adequately represents the "profound" aspect (hidden, not evident) of the reality of our universe. This structure cycles continuously (Figure 12).

Fig. 12. Profound cycle

References: N_{np} : profound negations

Figure 12 shows that the appearance of 00 means a 'turning point' (according to the geometric sense of the term, it is when a curve changes direction). The surface structure cycles to the right and this deep structure goes to the left.

4.0 MEDIATED NEGATION

"In this new universe, a second negation is not an affirmation." Mediated negation is the ideal tool to logically represent subjectivity. This is possible because it behaves like a distributor of binary systems, which in turn, defines the reflective process, the exclusive patrimony of the subject (S). This definition is somewhat ambiguous, but we could rescue it if we say that mediated negation behaves as a heterarchical (See Appendix A) distribution of hierarchical systems.

To apply mediated negation, we must have a set of elements greater than two. Starting from a trivalued system, six reflective patterns can be proposed that represent the possible relationships between the subject (S) and object (O) mediated by a transformation.

As we already said, each contexture (or unitary binary element) is composed of 'order' and 'disorder' or both. (Figure 13).

Fig. 13. Assignments table

order	disorder	
0	1	→ S(1)
1	0	→ O(2)
1	1	→ V(3)
		↑ decimal equivalent

According to Fig. 13, S and O are opposite elements (one is the negation of the other), as established by the Boolean (bivalued) logic.

Mediated negation distributes this tri-valued system generating a reflective and conservative loop, according to the following norm (Figure 14).

Fig. 14. Mediated negation

1 → 2
 3 → 1
 2 → 3

It means that: the second (N_2) denial of 1 is 2; that the N_2 of 3 is 1, and that the N_2 of 2 is 3.

This produces an exchange (and not an annulment) between elements (contextures) that after three negations take us to the initial element, closing the cycle that in this case, is levorotatory (L_v) (Figure 15).

Fig. 15. Levorotatory (L_v) and dextrorotatory (D_x) cycles

Thus, the S and the O are related through the change V, which binarily has components of both equally (11) (decimal = 3) In Figure 15 is represented a dextrorotatory cycle, where, the regime of negations is as follows: $1 \rightarrow 3 - 3 \rightarrow 2 - 2 \rightarrow 1$. If in the previous figure we replace the decimal numbers by their ontological equivalents we have, in the levorotatory: SOV, OVS, VSO. Here, despite being a levorotatory cycle, the different patterns are obtained, practically, by making a shift to the right of the extreme left element. The opposite happens in the other cycle: SVO, OSV, VOS, where, in spite of being a dextrorotatory cycle, to obtain the different patterns we have to move to the left the extreme right element. All these successions, from the logical point of view, are obtained by applying, in pairs, an XOR.

5.0 THE FOURTH ELEMENT

To constitute a true composite contexture (pattern of reality) 4 elements are needed. We provoke the 'generation' of the fourth element to form a tetravalent system. [A true system] This can be achieved if we apply the classical negation to a trivalent system affected (disturbed) by mediated negation. Now, in these circumstances, a binary negation does not have the same effect as that applied individually to a bivalent system. That is, it does not cancel it, but rather duplicates it since the non-correspondence of values leaves the third value without corresponding denied. Or in another way, it produces the appearance of another element that represents the 'absence of relation' between S and O. If V, by relating (interrelating) S and O represents a certain "organization", ∇ (binary = 00 - decimal = 0) accounts for certain "disorganization", which in reality represents a potential capacity for reorganization of the system (self-organization).

This new value does not take place in a trinary system. Therefore, it forces to generate another trinary loop that joins the previous one, although with particular characteristics. It is reflexive because it is structured by a mediated negation, but also cycles in the opposite direction and although the constitutive elements are the same as the original ones: S and O, they are not joined by a binary context that co-participates (co-presence). But it dissociates or releases them (co-absence), predicting the sequence (in jumps) of the complete system (6 valences) (distributed binary systems). Therefore, the 'displacement' of one element to another is carried out, not abruptly, but diffused (continuous). The opposing directions of rotation of these two cycles explain the isomeric complementarity they possess.

The following table establishes the steps specified above (Table II).

Table 2. Mediated negation – 4th element

P	$\sim P$	$\sim\sim P$	
3	1	2	→
2	3	0	→ 4 th element
1	2	1	

References: \oplus : mediated negation - \ominus : classic negation

We see, in Table 2, where the fourth value comes from. We must bear in mind that co-presence is a sign of heterarchy, not of hierarchy or transitivity, which makes possible co-ordination (organization), and therefore, self-reflection. This also allows the assembly of hierarchical (binary) (subordinate) and heterarchical (n-ary) (coordinates) systems.

6.0 UNIVERSAL AUTONOMOUS PATTERN (PAU)

If we assemble the two structures described in this universe that we have built, we will obtain a true system represented by an algebraic structure similar to that proposed by Boole, but with the significant difference that in our case, the “universe” represents a “permutation group “ (See Appendix A) as those defined by Galois in 1832. This last characteristic allows the structure proposed by the TL to be dynamic. That is, have evolution as time goes by, propitiated by the functions (relationships) that define it. This is why the logic that describes and explains this evolution is called “Transcursive Logic.” (Figure 16)

Fig. 16. PAU

References: \oplus : XOR - \ominus : Equivalence or XNOR - U: Universe

The previous scheme shows a “universe” represented by a complex system, the result of the assembly of evident and “hidden” manifestations. We have given this unit the name PAU (Universal Autonomous Pattern). In it, both its structure and its functions (relations) are expressed, that is, the “functional geometry” that aims to represent the smallest evidence of reality that a subject can conceive.

The PAU is, structurally speaking, a “Galois group,” but from the functional point of view it is a “Galois connection.” In 1832, Galois discovered the group he defines as a set of elements gathered by a composition operation (in our case \oplus) that applied to some elements of the set, gives us an element of the set. There is a neutral element in this set which, together with another of the same set, does not modify it (in our case ∇). There is an inverse operation that, when it is used together with the composition operation, gives the neutral element (in our case \odot). Finally, all the compositions are associative or independent of their grouping. These characteristics make this group a prototype of structure, given that it does not arise from the constitutive elements themselves, but from the permutative interrelationships between them. (Salatino, 2017, p 206).

A bivalued logic, like Boole's, is isomorphic. This isomorphism arises from the principle of the excluded third. The duality of conjunction and disjunction and the fact that in classical logic the dividing line between designation and non-designation coincides with the distinction between affirmation and negation (Ibidem, p.64).

In TL there is no such duality, because there is a "splice", a Galois connection (mathematically speaking), where disjunction and conjunction constitute the mediating opposition between another opposition: the two initial sets: S and O. This allows establishing a relationship between the objective (the known) and the subjective (the unknown), suggesting that the subjective should also correspond, in some way, to the real facts (Salatino, 2009). Nor is respected the principle of the excluded third, that which defines the hierarchy of binary systems, the heritage of

the monocontextural content. In a polycontextural logic such as TL, what links the different continents (or ontological niches - Salatino, 2008) is a heterárquica relation. Then, we could say that the TL represents a "heterarchical distribution of hierarchical or binary systems."

The bivalued logic is traditionally considered as the doctrine of the "laws of thought" (Boole, 1854). These laws are supposed to regulate the activity of a computational system or subject (S) which maps their environment. They refer, by designation, to an external world, and by self-reference, to themselves. In other words, the classical bivalent system represents two ontological places to which we can call, conventionally, "thought" and "being." (Günther, 1967) The above constitutes a double inconsistency. On the one hand, a binary system has room for a single ontological place, for some reason Günther called it "monocontextural."

On the other hand, a bivalued system like Boole's can only represent the object or the subject and one at a time. Furthermore, "thought" and "being" is not and can never be ontological or real places, not at least, from the subjective point of view (Salatino, 2009).

7.0 EXPANSION OF A FUNCTION

Returning to Boole's algebraic interpretation, we see that if x and y represented two different classes, $x + y$ represented a class that simultaneously contained all the individuals of x and y . The previous situation corresponds to the union of the "class logic." On the other hand, Boole interpreted the difference between classes $x - y$ as the class formed by all individuals of class x and none of class y . Which is equivalent to the intersection of "class logic." From all the above, the following pair of equalities arises:

$$\begin{aligned} x + (1 - x) &= 1 && \text{(1) (union)} \\ x \cdot (1 - x) &= 0 && \text{(2) (intersection)} \end{aligned}$$

Equation (1) tells us about the totality of individuals in a universe (those that belong to class x and those that do not, its complement, whose sum gives the unity).

Equation (2) expresses the Aristotelian "principle of non-contradiction," mathematically. (From Vado Virseda, 2017, page 56)

Boole not only included addition and subtraction between symbols in his algebra, but also division, which plays an important role in this method. The solution that, for example, gave to the equation $xw = y$, was $w = y / x$. Without clarifying what this operation means in logic, he interprets it by introducing the "expansion (or development) of a function."

The method of "expansion" works in the following way: if $f(x)$ is an algebraic expression, its expansion is given by:

$$f(x) = f(1)x + f(0)(1 - x) \tag{3}$$

The previous identity is established assuming the general form: $f(x) = ax + b(1 - x)$ (Bear in mind that $(1 - x) = y$). Then, a and b are determined by setting $x = 1$, $x' = 0$, $y = 1$ and $y' = 0$. For an expression with two variables, we have:

$$f(x, y) = f(1,1)xy + f(1,0)xy' + f(0,1)x'y + f(0,0)x'y' \tag{4}$$

Then, if $f(x, y) = y / x$, then:

$$y / x = 1/1 \cdot xy + 1/0 \cdot xy' + 0/1 \cdot x'y + 0/0 \cdot x'y' \tag{5}$$

The argument of Boole to equal a function with its expansion is at least defective because it assumes (without justifying it) that any function applied to its variables is linear (Nahin, 2013, p 69).

As we can see, the incompatibility between the Boolean algebra and the TL is multiple. In the first place, it strictly respects the basic principles of Aristotelian logic, something that does not happen in TL. Second, the use of the “expansion of a function” while describing, in some way, the “classes” that inhabit the universe analyzed does not succeed in establishing, completely, the relationships that are generated between them (4), nor does it say about the mechanism that allows one to "move" from one to another to scrutinize said universe (Figure 17).

Fig. 17. Expansion of a function

The PAU in Figure 18 clearly shows that the similarities between Boolean algebra and TL are nothing more than that, mere similarities.

Fig. 18. The logic within the logic

The fundamental nucleus of the TL (PAU) has a structure that consists as if it were a class (as a set of objects), a scope (or contexture) x , and a compliment (or content) y . On the other hand, from the “union by the differences” of x and y ($x \cup y$) and its opposite, the “separation by the similarities” of x and y ($x \cap y$).

From the functional point of view, this nucleus determines x and y , the simultaneous presence of what distinguishes them ($x + y$ or disjunction), and the simultaneous absence of what they have in common ($x \cdot y$ or conjunction). In this way, they form a “splice” of the union (\cup) of what differentiates them, with the separation (\cap) of what equals them, that is, that both belong to the set of real elements, or that they exist in the universe considered.

In this way the transformations that bind x and y that complete the PAU is defined. The "apparent or superficial transformation" (organization or co-presence) that we call "class," and the "hidden or deep transformation" (disorganization or co-absence) that we will call "category." It is important to clarify the terms used. The *transcurssive category* is neither the Aristotelian form of thought that reproduces something that occurs in objective reality, nor the pure concepts of the Kantian understanding, nor any of the three ontological categories of Peirce, nor those of Hegel, but the basis of the “sense” of the interrelations that keep the main actors in the subjective reality of a given universe (U). On the other hand, the *transcurssive class* is not a set of things that share some property, but on the contrary, it is the union of different objects that differ in some aspect.

Finally, what is obtained in the superficial level of the PAU (organization: union by the differences = 11) is projected in the profound level, (disorganization: separation by the similarities = 00) using the "inflection point" that means the appearance of the "fourth element." This projection

has as a goal to disorganize what has been obtained at a superficial level, and then reorganize it according to the requirements of the previous operation. Take into account that the surface level is what registers the "demands" of the environment, its "organization." Once the reorganization process has taken place at a deep level, what is obtained is again projected onto the surface, by the same 'channel' of the inflection point but traveled in the opposite direction. This last projection places the system at a new level of equilibrium with the environment, but now with a greater complexity that has allowed it to adapt to environmental demands.

8.0 CONCLUSIONS

In the analysis of basic principles on which Boole's algebra is based, we have discovered that some of the aspects of reality, that are revealed when we approach it from the subjective, are hidden between its values of truth and functions. That is, there is an "implicit logic" underlying the Boolean binary proposal, a logic that we have called 'transcurssive' because it leaves evidence of a certain evolution over time, of what affects an observer.

Among the findings we have to highlight: a) the existence of a complex system based, not on its constituent elements and a specific purpose, but on the interrelations that link its components. b) a systemic complexity that enables an adaptive dynamic response in front of the demands (inputs). c) the possibility of analyzing through the discovered structure, the relational situation of several binary systems, simultaneously (heterarchical distribution of hierarchical systems). d) the functional non-dependence of the structure concerning the observer (measurement process), as it is the case with any situation that is objectively addressed, and e) the advantage of being able to consider situations where more than two states are at stake, even if they are exclusive.

From the transcurssive perspective, an interesting panorama opens up of possible applications of this way of observing reality.

"From where, apparently there was nothing, the Transcurssive Logic arises."

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APPENDIX A

Class: Set of elements that have some property in common.

Discontinuous structure: It goes from one contexture to another by successive negations (at one time, all or nothing, 0 or 1). For this reason, the superficial structure is considered discrete or discontinuous.

Domain: Are the elements of the scope that satisfy a given function.

Double negation: $\sim\sim p = p$; $\sim 01 \rightarrow 10$; $\sim 10 \rightarrow 01$.

Galois Group: As we have already described in other works, here we will only list the basic properties of these groups. These groups must have: a) a composition operation; b) an operation opposite to that of composition; c) comply with the law of closure or closing; d) possess a neutral element; e) possess reverse elements; f) comply with the associative property; and g) comply with the law of the closure or closing of the conjugate.

Heterarchy: Refers to the situation of interdependence that must exist between different levels or subsystems in which different processes are developed simultaneously.

"Invisible" contexture: This situation, in the class logic, is characterized as a null scope and universal content. Or what is the same, a null class for logical reasons, since there are no elements that belong to its scope; all belong to its content. Here co-absence does not mean non-existence, which also supposes absence, the impossibility of presence, but represents the functional value of co-presence.

Laws of classical logic: The proposed structure does not follow the laws of classical logic, although the operations $\sim(10\sim 01)$ and $(01+\sim 01)$ represent principles or logical laws.

Ordered pairs: Thus, the ordered pair $\langle 0,1 \rangle$ in this order satisfies the relation 'tendency to go towards disorder' and the ordered pair $\langle 1,0 \rangle$: 'tendency to go towards order'; both relations raised in U.

Scope: That constituted by the elements of which a function is predicated.

Traditional negation: In this negation, what is done is to deny only the contexture A (01), with which it is canceled (disappears), transforming itself into the contexture B (10).